

Yashil

IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

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THE IMPROVEMENT OF FUNDING BUSINESS OPERATIONS FOR THE LOCAL ENTERPRISES IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN THROUGH ISSUING FINANCIAL SECURITIES BY MEANS OF THE TASHKENT STOCK EXCHANGE

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Abstract: The goal of this article is to show a meaning of the new funding ratio, which is the 60/40 funding ratio besides how it actually operates and the benefits to integrate the cooperation between the Tashkent Stock Exchange and the medium-sized, large private enterprises, after this would lead to spur local private firms to go public or issue corporate bonds in order to raise capital for business operations and other projects.

Key words: Tashkent Stock Exchange, medium-sized and large private companies, corporate loans, custodian banks, Central Bank of Uzbekistan, Clearstream, Euroclear, "Central Securities Depository" JSC, "National Clearing Centre" JSC, IPO.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolaning maqsadi 60/40 moliyalashtirish koeffitsientining ma'nosini, uning amalda qanday ishlashini va Toshkent fond birjasi bilan o'rta, yirik xususiy korxonalar o'rtasidagi hamkorlikni integratsiyalashning afzalliklarini ko'rsatishdan iborat. Shuningdek, mahalliy xususiy firmalarni biznes operatsiyalari va boshqa loyihalar uchun kapital jalb qilish maqsadida aksiyalar joylashtirish yoki korporativ obligatsiyalar chiqarishga yo'naltirishdan iborat.

Kalit so'zlar: Toshkent fond birjasi, o'rta va yirik xususiy kompaniyalar, korporativ kreditlar, kastodian banklar, O'zbekiston Markaziy Banki, Clearstream, Euroclear, "Qimmatli Qog'ozlar Markaziy Depozitariysi" AJ, "Milliy Kliring Markazi" AJ, IPO.

Аннотация: Цель данной статьи — показать значение коэффициента финансирования 60/40, а также то, как он на самом деле работает, и преимущества интеграции сотрудничества между Ташкентской фондовой биржей и средними и крупными частными предприятиями, поскольку это может побудить местные частные компании выходить на биржу или выпускать корпоративные облигации с целью привлечения капитала для коммерческой деятельности и других проектов.

Ключевые слова: Ташкентская Фондовая Биржа, средние и крупные частные компании, корпоративные кредиты, банки-кастодианы, Центральный Банк Узбекистана, Clearstream, Euroclear, АО «Центральный Депозитарий Ценных Бумаг», АО «Национальный Клиринговый Центр», IPO.

INTRODUCTION

As it is widely known that in Uzbekistan, almost all private firms use commercial loans in order to finance any kind of expenses even when it comes to expand or diversify output, they select banking loans instead of going public or issuing bonds. Therefore, I realized that it is necessary to create funding program that would make local private businesses, mostly middle and huge companies to seek out an alternative source of financing own projects such as selling share of stock or placing corporate bonds by means of the Tashkent Stock Exchange. Firstly, there should be some credit limits for medium as well as large companies since many medium-sized and large firms are highly granted by banking loans, which makes difficult for them to look for alternative sources of funding. Besides, many private enterprises are totally dependent to corporate loans resulting in a strict restriction of financing own operations. For this reason, it is crucially important to impose some certain restrictions in funding middle and large enterprises via corporate loans of commercial banks.

LITERATURE REVIEW

1. Professor of Finance, University of Oxford. Leverage International Best Practices: "Uzbekistan should adopt international standards for corporate governance, financial reporting, and investor protection to attract foreign capital. This will enhance the credibility of local enterprises and make their securities more appealing

to global investors.”

2. Professor of Economics, Harvard University. Develop a Robust Legal Framework: “A strong legal framework is essential for a functioning stock market. Uzbekistan should prioritize the development of laws and regulations that protect investors, ensure fair market practices, and facilitate dispute resolution.”

3. Professor of Entrepreneurship, Stanford University. Foster a Culture of Entrepreneurship: “To encourage more local enterprises to access the stock market, Uzbekistan needs to foster a culture of entrepreneurship and innovation. This can be achieved through initiatives such as startup incubators, mentorship programs, and access to venture capital.”

4. Professor of Finance, University of Tokyo. Expand the Range of Securities: “Beyond equities, Uzbekistan should explore other types of securities, such as corporate bonds and sukuk (Islamic bonds), to cater to diverse investor preferences and provide alternative financing options for local enterprises.”

5. Professor of Economics, London School of Economics. Enhance Market Liquidity: “A liquid market is crucial for attracting investors. Uzbekistan should implement measures to increase trading volume and improve market efficiency, such as reducing transaction costs, promoting market-making activities, and enhancing market infrastructure.”

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In the implementation of these research works, widely used methods in scientific research methodology were used. In the process of scientific analysis, these scientific research methods, in particular, observation, generalization, grouping, comparison, analysis, and synthesis and analysis methods were widely used.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

So, it is necessary to create a funding program for middle and large private companies based on the 60/40 funding ratio, to be more precise, a company willing to raise capital for its project, would be allowed to take out only 40% of estimated its total project's cost and the rest of 60% would have to go public by selling its stocks or issuing bonds, but in any all these operations would be accomplished through the Tashkent Stock Exchange. What is more, there should be taken some action to assist in an IPO process from the authorities of the Tashkent Stock Exchange by covering underwriting outlays partly or even fully so as to stimulate local enterprises to seek out funds beyond corporate loans.

The 60/40 funding ratio (medium-sized and large firms)

This technique does appear to be one of the most appropriate way to spur medium-sized as well as large private enterprises to fund the rest of 60% beyond a corporate loan market, since many businesses in Uzbekistan, mostly middle and big firms, are highly dependent to commercial banks' loans when it comes to finance their own projects or even operations. For instance, a firm (medium-sized or large) is about to purchase a contemporary machine-tool in order to boost output by diminishing producing outlays, and therefore the company would need to borrow funds to acquire the machine-tool for a certain amount of money. Then, the business would apply to a corporate loan, and according to the 60/40 funding ratio, only 40% of demanded

amount of capital from the credit application form would be endorsed by a bank clerk, the rest of 60% would have to be rejected since the enterprise would be forced to seek out an alternative source of financing such as placing corporate bonds or selling stocks with the assistance of the Tashkent Stock Exchange.

Similarly, there should be taken some counter steps from the authorities of Tashkent Stock Exchange by covering underwriting expenses of local companies IPO processes for the purpose of encouraging local firms (middle and big) to get involved in raising funds through the stock market. And by doing this, it is likely to proliferate demand for investment within local entrepreneurs in Uzbekistan. Even there has been made several contributions for developing Capital Market Infrastructure to stimulate local companies to attract external capital by selling securities through the stock market. In particular, according to RP-291 “On Additional Measures to Develop the Capital Market”¹, “Central Securities Depository” JSC created under Central Bank of Uzbekistan, in addition, corresponding accounts opened at the Central Bank of Uzbekistan for “Central Securities Depository” JSC as well as “National Clearing Centre” JSC making local companies’ securities more attractive for foreign investors to invest in. Consequently, the 60/40 funding ratio is expected to be implemented beneficially for all stock market participants, in other words, rights of both issuer and investor would be under the protection of the Central Bank of Uzbekistan, apart from this, local middle or large enterprises could attract foreign currencies to make a payment for purchases from abroad.

Moreover, there should be taken some measures of offering middle or large companies’ securities willing to raise capital from foreign investors, by representing them to foreign nominees such as Clearstream, Euroclear and other huge custodian banks which own foreign nominal accounts at “Central Securities Depository” JSC, or at “National Clearing Centre” JSC. In addition, it is necessary to create stock classes² that would have to be divided into two main categories as “external” and “internal” since almost all foreign investors generally prefer to invest in US dollar nominated assets for the purposes of avoiding a national currency depreciation when it comes to withdraw dividends or coupon payments. So, the “external” class would be issued in foreign currency, in our case, this would be in US dollars, how about the “internal” class, of course, they would be placed in the national currency, UZS.

Simultaneously, middle and large private businesses would take advantage of this opportunity since they could attract funds in both national as well as foreign currencies, meanwhile it could result in widening a cooperation between local enterprises and international financial institutions that might add numerous sources of capital to finance corporate projects and other business operations. As emphasized, many private companies, medium-sized and huge ones, still rely on the corporate loans provided by local commercial banks. Thus, the 60/40 funding ratio could likely provide a promising choice to diversify ways of raising capital by means of the Tashkent Stock Exchange.

Allocated Corporate Loans in the Republic of Uzbekistan in trillion UZS (2021-2024)³

1 <https://lex.uz/ru/docs/6590029>

2 Based on the author’s development from his own PhD thesis, first chapter.

3 Based on the author’s development. Data gathered from the Internet.

The bar graph above does represent allocated corporate loans in the Republic of Uzbekistan in trillion UZS between 2021 and 2024. In general, it can be seen that the total corporate loans allocated within 4 years increased from 14,8 to 18,02 trillion UZS, and out of these figures it is clear that corporate loans for medium-sized as well as large private companies accounted for 8,6 trillion UZS in 2021, and the number reached 13,7 trillion UZS by the August 1st (2024). Overall, it is obvious that more than a half of the total allocated corporate loans in each year taken by middle and large private companies showing how these private businesses are dependent to commercial banking loans when it comes to raise capital for business operations, or for the expansion of produced goods and services.

Next is the same information about allocated corporate loans by percentage and based on the bar graph, in 2021, corporate loans provided to the medium-sized and large private companies made up 58%, consequently this figure has attained 76% by the August 1st (2024). Thus, the proportion of middle as well as large private enterprises within 4 years only expanded from 58% to 76%, between 2021-2024, respectively.

CONCLUSION

By and large, the 60/40 funding ratio could promote medium-sized and large private firms to seek out alternative sources of capital raising by going public by means of IPO procedures, that is to say, to sell share of stocks to investors or placing corporate bonds, regardless of two options mentioned above, in any cases, all these processes would be accomplished with the help of the Tashkent Stock Exchange resulting in the expansion of a number of quoted companies on the listing board. Last but not least, there should be taken a similar step from the side of the Tashkent Stock Exchange by covering IPO expenses for those middle and huge private companies.

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